

Effect of Activity-Based Strategy on Performance in Islamic Studies Concept among Secondary School Students In Kaduna State, Nigeria

HAJIYA, Gambo Zakari (Ph.D.)¹

asmauzakari70@gmail.com

08060766412

FATIMA, Bello (Ph.D.)¹

fatimabello2018@gmail.com

08163552251

ALIYU, Hamza Musa (Ph.D.)¹

hamzamusa434@gmail.com

07038080071

¹Curriculum and Instruction Department, Federal University of Education, Zaria

Abstract

The current teaching methods employed by Islamic studies teachers in Kaduna state is grossly inadequate and more of teacher-centered approach. Also, the negative attitude of students towards learning of Islamic studies is partially as a result of poor teaching methods employed by teachers' right from the onset. Thus, deems it fit to investigate on the effectiveness of Activity -Based strategy on Performance in Islamic Studies concept among secondary school students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State. The objective of the study was to compare the performance of Islamic studies students taught with activity-based methods and those taught with conventional method. One research question and corresponding null hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. A sample of 2 Senior Secondary Schools within Zaria Metropolis were randomly selected from the target population of 3,753 and were assigned into experimental and control group. The experimental group were exposed to treatment package i.e. taught with activity-based method while control group were taught with conventional method. Instrument used for the study was Islamic Studies Performance and Evaluation Test (ISPET). Descriptive statistics was used to answer research question and t-test statistical analysis to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings from the study revealed that there is significance difference in mean performance score of students taught Islamic concept using activity-based strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method. The t-value is -17.95, while the sig (p) value is 0.000 ($P < 0.005$) thus, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. In view of the findings, it is concluded that activity-based teaching methods improves performance by allowing students to actively participate in the learning experience rather than being passive listeners. Thus, it is recommended that since activity-based methods has been

found to improve students' performance in Islamic studies, teachers, should be encouraged to actively involve students into participatory activities rather than passive listeners.

Key words: *Activity based method, Conventional Method, Performance, Islamic Studies*

Introduction

Teaching is an interactive process through which knowledge, values and skills are shared with students with a view of improving understanding and ability to bring about desirable learning. Thus, teacher initiates the communication and interaction through proper instructional process and methods. The Federal republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) in the National Policy on Education, emphasized the adequate choice of teaching methods by teachers so as to solve education problems and enhance students learning. Islamic studies as a subject offered in secondary schools in Nigeria involves the study of human life and moral education. It stresses the relationship of man and his various components such as environment, social and political settings, economic transaction, moral and spiritual obligations. Fundamentally, it involves the translation of the Islamic fundamentals to practical aspect of worship. Among the objectives of teaching Islamic studies according to the National Policy on Education (2013) is to lay a sound basis for moral habit as well scientific, critical and creative thinking.

In view of this, Islamic studies curriculum needs to be properly and effectively implemented in order to achieve the desired objectives for which it is intended. Thus, no discussion of curriculum is complete without effective and proper implementation of the curriculum. There are varieties of teaching methods depending on the situation, learner's level as well as the subject matter. It can be teacher-centered, learner-centered or a mixed. Ahmad and Aziz (2000) described teacher-centered method as a method with the teacher as an expert and authority in presenting information, students' active participation is minimal. In contrast, learner-centered method is associated with active participation of students, in the learning process through discussion intellectual engagement, critical and creative skills. These methods include activity-based, inquiry, collaborative, project etc. furthermore, according to Chika (2012), connect students world with learning pursuit in the classroom.

Activity-based method is a teaching method whereby the learners are actively engaged in the learning process rather than absorbing facts from the lessons. The learners must be part and parcel of the learning process. According to Dhar and Faize (2011), teaching should help the learner acquired blend of theory and practical skills. Furthermore, Okwudishi (2011) defines activity-based method as a procedure adopted by teacher to teach through activity in which

the students participate actively and bring about efficient learning experience. Learning by doing is the main focus. This affects the students' opportunity to interact with one another and acquire some social skills, cooperate, accepted or tolerate one another and how to work as a team (Guga & Bawa, 2015).

As Islamic studies aimed at inculcating moral, discipline and ethical values into the minds of the learners in order to abide by the teachings of the religion therefore, the spiritual and moral training are regarded as fundamentals and should educate the learner in the development of such fundamental in a practical manner though various activities concerning matters relating to recitation of the Qur'an, performance of Ibadah including the five pillars of Islam all are practical in nature. Hence, this calls for a student-centered and collaborative learning process and for teaching and learning situation to be successful both the teacher and the learners have some activities to perform (Guga & Bawa, 2015). More so, education should aim at helping the child to acquired appropriate skills, activities and competencies both mental and physical as equipment for the individual to live and contribute to the development of the society (NPE, 2013). This can only be achieved when Islamic studies is properly and adequately taught using appropriate method such as learner centered approach. It is in this regard that Emeh (2011), posited that the current teaching methods employed in secondary schools by teachers in Nigeria are grossly inadequate and are more of teacher-centered. In the same vein Ibrahim and Aliyu (2011) added that Islamic studies teachers have difficulties. In identifying other appropriate teaching methods strategies and approaches to teach the subject. Moreover, Olatubosun and Taminowa (2013), suggest that, Islamic studies teachers should vary their methodologies of teaching. Despite this, conventional methods remain the most popular methods which are considered inappropriate. Also based on the complexity of the curriculum, some of the teachers skip some aspects of the curriculum that are learner centered approach which could be due to lack of competence in treating them.

Closely related to that National Teachers Institute in Melissa (2009) explains that, Islamic Studies teachers under Islamic Education System are usually trained under conventional teaching methods. In addition to this, Fafunwa (2014) confirms that the negative attitude of students towards learning Islamic studies is partially as a result of poor teaching method employed by teacher's right from the onset. In view of the above, there is need to investigate on the effectiveness of learner centered approach (activity-based) method on performance of secondary school students in Islamic studies in Kaduna State with a view of establishing how such methods will enable teachers easily diagnose the problems of individual learners and

allow them to evaluate themselves and participate actively in the teaching and learning process.

Objective of the Study

This research is designed to:

- i. Determine the mean difference in performance scores of students taught Islamic studies concepts using activity-based strategy and those exposed to conventional method in Zaria metropolis, kaduna State

Research Question

- i. What is the mean difference in performance scores of students taught Islamic studies concepts using activity-based strategy and those exposed to conventional method in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna state?

Null Hypothesis

Ho₁. There is no significant difference in performance scores of students taught Islamic studies concepts using activity-based strategy and those exposed to conventional method in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna state.

Methodology

The study was carried out to find the effect of activity -based strategy on performance in Islamic studies concept among secondary school students in Kaduna state, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose, the study was conducted in some secondary schools within Zaria Metropolis using SSII Islamic studies students as the sample of the study. The target population comprised all SSII students offering Islamic studies in Zaria Metropolis with the total population of three thousand seven hundred and fifty-three (3,753) students.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample of one hundred and sixty-eight (168) SSII Islamic studies students from two (2) secondary schools were randomly selected from the target population and were assigned into 2 groups (Experimental and Control). Purposive sampling technique was employed to ensure subject chosen with similar background and expose to similar infrastructure. Out of the sample of 168 SSII Islamic studies students, 75 were grouped under experimental groups

while 93 under control groups. Experimental groups were taught using activity-based strategy while control group were taught using conventional methods of teaching.

Instrumentation

Instrument used was Islamic Studies Performance and Evaluation Test (ISPET) which consist of 30 multiple choice objective test questions. Students were made to select correct answer from the four options lettered A-D. The items were carefully drawn to ensure that it felt within the scope of SSII syllabus and had been selected from the purpose of the study. It was also referred to the seasoned and experienced educationist to ensure their correctness, clarity, appropriateness and standard for SSII students.

The experimental (activity-based strategy) and control (conventional method) groups took a pre-test before the administration of the instrument. This was done to determine baseline equivalency between the two groups with respect to the Islamic studies concepts to be taught. The pre-test results were used to check if there was a significance difference in the academic performance of the two groups. The experimental group were exposed to treatment over a period of three weeks while the control group were taught with the conventional method.

Presentation of Results

The results for the study were presented according to the guiding research question and hypothesis. Analysis of the pre-test and post-test were collected while data collected was by means of the students taught with activity-based strategy and those taught with conventional teaching method. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research question while t-test was used in analyzing the pre-test and post-test scores.

Research Question

1. What is the effect of activity -based strategy on performance in Islamic studies concept among secondary school students when compared with conventional method in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna state?

Table 1: Paired sample t-test showing differences in post-test scores of experimental and control groups

(Effect of Activity-Based Strategy on Performance in Islamic Studies Concept among ... Zakari, H. G. Et. al. 2025)

Source	Group	Mean	N	SD	df	t	Sig. (2 tailed)
Post-test score	Experimental	22.11	75	2.62	166	-17.95	.000
Post-test score	Control	16.17	93	2.53			

Statistical data presented in the above table revealed the post-test mean score of 22.11 for experimental group with standard deviation of 2.62 while the control post-test mean scores is 16.17 with standard deviation of 2.53. The result shows that students taught with collaborative and activity-based methods had a better performance in their post-test scores compared to the performance of those taught with conventional methods. Also, the t-value is -17.95, while the sig. (P) value is 0.000 ($P < 0.005$). Based on this, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected because there was a significant difference in the post-test scores of students taught Islamic studies with collaborative and activity-based methods, as compared with those taught with conventional methods.

Discussion of Finding

With reference to the research question and null hypothesis, it is observed that significant difference exists in the performance of students taught Islamic studies with activity-based strategy compared to their counterpart taught with conventional method. This was further confirmed by the paired sample t-test results in table 3 which shows that the difference in the post-test score is significant. This finding confirmed the result of Iwuji (2012) that students exposed to activity-based teaching strategy achieved significantly higher than their counterpart. The findings also upheld that of Khan, Muhammad, Ahmed and Sa’eed (2012) which revealed that there was a positive impact of activity-based strategy in development of higher order skills in the students therefore most effective than the traditional method.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from the study, conclusion was reached that activity-based teaching strategy improves students’ performance and allow students to actively participate in the learning experience rather than sit as passive listeners. It was deduced that students taught Islamic studies with activity-based strategy significantly performed better than their counterpart taught with conventional methods.

Recommendation

Based on the above the study recommended that:

(Effect of Activity-Based Strategy on Performance in Islamic Studies Concept among ... Zakari, H. G. Et. al. 2025)

- i. Since activity-based strategy has been found to improve students' performance in Islamic studies, teachers should encourage to involve students into participatory activities rather than allowing them to become passive recipients.

References

- Ahmad, F & Aziz, J. (2009). Students' Perceptions of the Teacher's Teaching of Literature Communicating and Understanding through the eyes of the Audience. *European Journal of Social Science*, 7(3), 17-39.
- Aliyu, A., (2015). Effect of Inquiry Method on Academic Performance of Junior Secondary Schools' Students in Islamic religious Studies in Katsina State, Nigeria. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis. Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Chika, P.O., (2012). The extent of students' responses in the classroom. *International Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*. 2(1), 22-37
- Dhar, M. A. & Faize, F. A. (2011). Effect of the Availability and the Use of Instructional Materials on Academic Performance of Students in Pujab Pakistan. *Middle Eastern Finance Economic Journal Issue*, 53: (2), 110-120
- Emeh, J.U. (2011). Curriculum Review: Reaction from Education Stakeholders in South-South state of Nigeria. *Global Journal of Human Social Studies*, 11(09). 32-42
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). National Policy on Education. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Guga, A. & Bawa, M.R. (2015). Curriculum and Instruction. Zaria: Kareem & Guga Publishers.
- Ibrahim, J. (2013). Effects of Inquiry Method on Performance of Junior Secondary Schools Students in Islamic Studies, Kaduna State, Nigeria. An Unpublished M.Ed Thesis. Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Iwuji, N.P. (2012). Effects of Activity-Based Teaching Strategy on Academic Achievement and Retention in Basic Science Concepts among Junior Secondary School Students in Kaduna State. An Unpublished M.Ed Thesis, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Khan, M., Muhammad, N., Maqsood, R. & Sa'eed, F. (2012). Impacts of Activity-Based teaching on Students Academic Achievements in Physics at Secondary Level. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 3 (1), 146-150 from [www.sayap.org.pl/c/journals/Arint./vol.3\(1\)2012\(3.1-19\)pdfon13/06/2015](http://www.sayap.org.pl/c/journals/Arint./vol.3(1)2012(3.1-19)pdfon13/06/2015)
- Oktubosun, A. (2013). Islamic Studies in Nigeria: Problems and Prospects. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3 (2), 179-185.

(Effect of Activity-Based Strategy on Performance in Islamic Studies Concept among ... Zakari, H. G. Et. al. 2025)

Okwudishu, A. U. (2011). Trainers Guide to Reuses of the Manual of Best Practices and Methods of Facilitating in Basic Literacy programme. A Lead paper Presented during a workshops on developing Manual of Best Practice at Enugu. Nigeria.